

Geospatial Assessment of Waste Dumpsites in Kinshasa: Health and Environmental Risks

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Abstract

Over a hundred dumpsites were recorded between 2015 and 2025 in Kinshasa, the Capital city of the Democratic Republic of Congo. Studies investigating health and environmental risks along with the impacts of these sites are scarce. The current study analyzes the spatial distribution of solid waste dumpsites in Kinshasa, the correlation between their density and hotspots with population indicators, their proximity to water bodies and buildings and the inherent risks. Results show higher dumpsites' density in the communes of Bumbu and Makala. Regression analysis shows no meaningful correlation between dumpsites hotspots and demographic metrics. Proximity analysis reveals 53 connection segments between water points and 20 dumpsites within 300-meter buffers, with 37 intersection points with water bodies, 4 with riverbanks, 6 with wetlands and 6 with reservoirs. The major rivers at risk include the Congo River in Pool Malebo, along with N'djili river. Three sites revealed higher risks (≥ 5 connection points). Regarding the proximity of human settlements, 172 dumpsites count in their vicinity (300 m) thousands of settlements involved in urbanites' daily activities, including houses, schools, churches, hospitals. Among these, 11 sites indicate critical public health exposure with a count of >12000 buildings (22%), and 41 sites with 26674 buildings (47%). Adequate governance and engineering interventions to manage existing dumpsites are urgently needed to mitigate the health and environmental risks, effects and impacts of municipal solid waste on residents and other urban ecosystems.

Keywords: *municipal solid waste, dumpsites, geospatial assessment, environmental risk, health exposure.*

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Introduction

Waste dumping has been practiced in human societies for several generations (Barles, 2014). The accumulation of unregulated dumps over time caused unprecedented health and environmental crises, in Europe and America in the 1860s through the middle of the 19th century. The advent of these crises triggered the emergence and significant advances in legal frameworks for waste

management (Barles, 2014; Remigios, 2010; Scheinberg et al., 2010; Wilson et al., 2015), further amplified with the birth of the environmental movement in the 1960s. Studies signal earlier waste regulations in Greece in 500 B-C (Barles, 2014). Global nations have undertaken and continue to adopt national legislations organizing the protection of the environment and public health, as well as the management of waste, including measures pertaining to on-land disposal methods (Barles, 2014; Gonzenbach & Coad, 2007; Remigios, 2010; Scheinberg et al., 2010). At the heart of these dynamic legal frameworks, the abandonment of waste in inappropriate and unauthorized places is prohibited, and therefore, subject to penalties (Navasardova et al., 2020; Uhri & Nemes, 2024). However, despite the prohibitions, littering and waste dumping are still massively practiced in various societal settings, although heightened among the residents of developing countries (Adedinni et al., 2023; Bangani et al., 2025; Bundhoo, 2018).

In recent years, uninterrupted, and amplified industrialization, coupled with urbanization, exploding populations, unrestrained production and consumerism are birthing every year over 2 billion tons of municipal solid waste globally. The projections posit an increase by approximately 80 % to 3.8 billion tons by 2050 (UNEP, 2024; Vuppaladadiyam et al., 2024). This waste deluge all over the world further exacerbates the challenges of its management, especially in countries struggling with inadequate infrastructure, technology and weak governance systems. These challenges are evidenced among other things, by the proliferation of illegal and uncontrolled waste dumpsites (Bundhoo, 2018; Chuma et al., 2024; Ekeu-Wei et al., 2018). These debris mounds pile up organic materials, plastic, glasses, radioactive and potentially explosive substances which form the municipal solid waste generated within households, schools, hospitals, markets, industries, and farms. The heaps of waste materials, given their complex composition, are prone to undergo numerous chemical reactions and thereby emit liquid and gaseous toxins that pollute soil, water bodies, and air, with associated health risks for humans and other ecosystems (Ekeu-Wei et al., 2018; Maturano et al., 2024; UNEP, 2024). Fazzo et al. (2023) investigated the health impacts of wastes dumpsites in 38 municipalities in a City from South Italy and reported high mortality and hospitalization risk from cancer, stomach, kidney, liver, lungs and heart diseases among the communities residing in proximity to contaminated sites. In a recent review on the health and environmental impacts of uncontrolled major dumpsites in Africa, Omokaro *et al.* (2024) reported cases of surface and groundwater contamination, air pollution, malaria, parasitaemia and blood disorders amongst the neighbouring communities.

Similar to most cities of the developing world (Nagpure, 2019; Nwankwoala & Offor, 2018), waste dumping ranks high among the health and environmental challenges facing Kinshasa, the capital city of the Democratic Republic of Congo (DR Congo). This behaviour is illegal in accordance with the Congolese Constitution -article 53 on the fundamental right related to environmental sanitation and the Law on Basic Principles for Environmental Protection dating 2011, in its chapters 6, 7 and 8, as well as other rules covering public health and urban sanitation (Parliament, 2006, 2011). Despite these laws and regulations, waste dumping remains widely practiced in Kinshasa. In the DR Congo, estimates on the volume of daily municipal solid waste generation and management are scarce and often extrapolated from reduced units of the population across different case studies. Kang *et al.* (2023) report approximately 7800 tons of municipal solid waste (MSW) generated every day in 2023 in Kinshasa, composed mainly of organic materials (65%), plastic (15%), metal (7%), textiles (6%), inert waste (4%), glass (2%) and other materials (1%). Merging different collection rates from 3 studies conducted in Kinshasa in 2015, 2020 and 2023, we obtained an average collection rate of 27% (Kang et al., 2023; Mangenda et al., 2020; Simatele & Etambakonga, 2015). Of the uncollected amounts, the lowest part undergoes valorization through composting and recycling, while the bigger proportion is dumped, buried or burned (Katembo et al., 2025; Mangenda et al., 2020). In a study covering the 22 municipalities of Kinshasa, Mangenda et al. (2020) reported that 34.4% of the waste generated in Kinshasa is dumped on roads, in rivers and any other available

public space, while Kang *et al.*(2023) for the part recorded a fraction of 33% left for dumping. As a result, wild and/or unengineered waste dumpsites proliferate across the City of Kinshasa, on roadsides, within open and closed drainage pipelines, on vacant lots, and any available natural environments including on riverbanks, and within water bodies(Diambu & Mehmet, 2024; Kubanza & Simatele, 2015).

Consequently, studies conducted in Kinshasa report contamination of water bodies and soil, affecting ecosystem's structure, functions and human health(Kang et al., 2023; Kang et al., 2024). Assessing water quality in Tshuenge River in Kinshasa, Sifa et al.(2024) found alarming values for water quality parameters, indicating pollution and undrinkability. This study lists waste dumping in rivers and their vicinity as the major causes of pollution in Tshuenge river, along with untreated wastewater discharges. Congo River's raw water quality was examined in 2019, under the leadership of the Ministry in charge of Energy and hydraulic resources, during an environmental impact assessment for a water pumping and drinking water treatment plant construction project(REGIDESO, 2019). Water samples were taken from three stations: R8-Maluku, R2-Ngaliema, and R4-Kinsuka. Overall, the study findings revealed varying pollution profile and intensity including high turbidity, microbial contamination with total coliforms, *E. coli*, fecal streptococci and revivable microorganisms, as well as elevated concentrations of some metals such as iron, manganese, zinc and aluminum. These investigations mention wastewater and solid waste dumping into the river among the major causes of the alarming pollution status of the Congo River at the selected locations. Magenda et al.(2022) studied the conditions of the soil from a 60 m² dumpsite located in Kasa-vubu municipality, and receiving approximately 100 tons of municipal solid waste daily. The study samples[30] were drawn at different locations within the vicinity of the dumpsite. Their findings demonstrate severe pollution. Another study by(Mavakala et al., 2022) found relatively high concentration of Scandium, Chromium, Cobalt, Copper, Zinc, Arsenic, Cadmium, Lead and Mercury in soil from selected 15 waste dumpsites in Kinshasa. Ngweme et al.(2020) found high metal concentrations in *A. viridis* leaf in Kinshasa, evidencing crops contamination as an impact of degraded water quality from waste pollution, which in turn has adverse effects on urban agriculture.

Few studies attempted to assess the linkages between the existence of waste dumpsites in the city and the health of the urbanites, emphasizing the evident and/or potential contribution of waste dumpsites' pollution on human health(Kang et al., 2024; Nsindu et al., 2023; Rodriguez et al., 2022). In these studies, malaria and typhoid fever hold higher ranks, exhibiting strong correlation with waste dumpsites' proximity to human settlements as a contributing factor to the spread of *Salmonella Typhi*, *Psalmodium parasites* and another wide range of pathogens contaminating and decimating neighboring communities. Inadequate sanitation and defective waste management systems were reported as main causes of 31,342 cholera cases and 230 deaths in the DR Congo in 2023(Kang et al., 2023). Flooding is one of the major environmental hazards frequently recorded in the DR Congo and in Kinshasa. The events intensify over the years following the significant changes and in rainfall patterns. Often simply recorded in government reports and press releases, these events are strongly linked with waste management challenges, including illegal dumping of solid waste in drainage pipes and in rivers(Mufungizi et al., 2024). Sendezo *et al.*(2024) selected Kalamu municipality to assess the linkages between waste dumping and flooding hazards in Kinshasa. Their findings demonstrate that waste dumping in rivers and clogged drainage pipes represent 63.6% of the causes of flooding in Kalamu. Moreover, Kang *et al.* (2023) reported that approximately 640,673 tons of CO₂ emit annually in the DR Congo are linked with waste management practices.

While scholars increasingly investigate waste management challenges in African cities and in Kinshasa, fine-scale spatial patterns of waste dumpsites remain poorly documented. Thus, the

current study pursues a three-fold objective comprising: (1) mapping dumpsite density across the 24 communes that constitute Kinshasa city; (2) test correlations between demographic metrics and dumpsites proliferation and density; and (3) conduct a health and environmental risk assessment of the identified sites through proximity analysis using water bodies and human settlements. Through spatial analysis and risk quantification, this study seeks to offer governance insights into environmental risk prioritization and a methodological approach to understanding the linkages between dumpsites distribution, demographic metrics, and urban primary ecosystems.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

The current study focuses on Kinshasa, a province and the capital city of the DR Congo, located on the southern bank of the Congo River between 4°17'30" and 4°30'00" South and 15°12' and 15°30' East. Kinshasa covers an area of 9,965 km², with an elevation ranging between 275 and 370 meters above sea level. The city portrays a tropical climate with consistently warm temperatures, with average daytime highs reaching 30–35°C for most of the year, with nighttime lows around 21–22°C. At times, monthly absolute maximum temperatures often surpass 35°C, the humidity above 70%, average annual rainfall of approximately 1,529 mm, and the soil's average annual water balance of 1,362 mm (Lenzo et al., 2024). Of the 26 provinces that constitutes the DR Congo, approximately 17% of the total population (~100 M) lives in Kinshasa (~17 M) as of the 2024 statistics. In addition to the fertility rate at 3.4/woman in 2023, Kinshasa receives the highest number of internal migrants given the wide socio-economic divide and unbalanced development between cities of the DR Congo (INS, 2024; Simatele & Etambakonga, 2015). This massive population classifies Kinshasa among the densely populated cities in Africa., (Bédécarrats, 2019). Figure 1 below shows Kinshasa's location in the DR Congo.

Figure 1. Study area Map

Source: the authors

To-date the DR Congo lacks a dedicated policy for waste management, while waste legislation is mainly organized by the Law No. 11/009 of July 9, 2011, as modified to date, establishing the fundamental principles of environmental protection (Parliament, 2011). This law categorizes waste

and determines the core principles for the management of each type of waste, the prohibited practices and penalties, and refers to reinforcement measures for precise implementation guidelines. However, over a decade later, these regulations are yet to be enacted. Other relevant rules are scattered across laws and regulations on health and urban sanitation, mining activities, and urban planning. The inadequate services are evidenced through limited, irregular and in some areas, a lack of basic services for collection in a context of pronounced environmental injustice (Kubanza, 2017; Simatele & Etambakonga, 2015).

The institutional framework for waste management in the province derives mainly from the Constitution, then the Law n° 08/012 of July 31st, 2008, on the free administration of the provinces, in its article 37(13), and the Organic Law n° 08/016 of October 7th, 2008, on the composition, organization, and operation of Decentralized Territorial Entities and their relations with the State and the Provinces (Parliament, 2008a, 2008b). In practice, other stakeholders intervene, including nonprofits and the private sector. Their actions are mostly directed towards awareness and waste collection in exchange for monetary subscription.

In Kinshasa, urban sanitation and waste management are under “Kin Bopeto”, a local government’s program launched in 2019 (Ndala, 2024). Kinshasa Bopeto program seeks to increase the effectiveness and efficiency of waste collection in Kinshasa, mitigating waste dumping and increasing the rate of waste valorization. However, this program, similar to its predecessors fails to bring about the expected shifts in practices and the associated consequences. Several causes are highlighted as contributors to this failure, among these weak investments, inadequate infrastructure, and low awareness. Thus, despite the existence of this program, illegal dumping remains widely practiced across the city of Kinshasa and wild dumpsites continue their proliferation.

Methods

To investigate the spatial distribution of waste dumpsites in Kinshasa, we compiled data from three assessments conducted between 2015 and March 2025 (Kang et al., 2024; LUKAFULU, 2025; Mavakala et al., 2022). The identified sites include active and inactive illegal waste dumpsites, transfer stations from which waste is actually stockpiled indefinitely, and regulated open dumpsites. In addition, we rely on freely accessible online geographic information system (GIS) datasets for features such as administrative boundaries, hydrography, and human settlements. The key sources are GADM, GEOFABRIK// Home and the Humanitarian Data Exchange (HDX).

The key Software used for data analysis includes QGIS 3.44, Origin Pro 2025b and MS Excel. Analysis procedures encompass nearest neighborhood analysis, kernel density estimation, zonal statistics, Pearson correlation, regression analysis, composite health risk calculation, buffer analysis, intersection calculation, points in polygon counting.

- Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) is a renowned non-parametric statistical technique, extensively used to assess probability density function of a dataset (Chen, 2017).

$$\hat{f}(x) = \frac{1}{nh} \sum_{i=1}^n K\left(\frac{x-x_i}{h}\right) \quad (1)$$

where K = quartic kernel, h = bandwidth, n = dumpsite points.

Adaptive bandwidth approach was implemented (Eckert-Gallup & Martin, 2016), using *scale-of-analysis* choice informed by nearest-neighbor distances. Through nearest neighbor analysis

of dumpsites points in the study datasets, the clustering patterns of dumpsites were revealed including the observed distance, expected mean distance, nearest neighborhood index (NN index) and the Z-score. The chosen bandwidth is approximately 1.5–2 times the typical inter-site spacing, to capture commune-scale variations in dumpsite density with minimum smoothing. Bandwidth calculation was carried out as:

$$h = \max(1.3 \times \text{Observed}_{MD}, 1000) \text{ meters} \quad (2)$$

where Observed_{MD} is the mean nearest-neighbor distance.

KDE was computed in QGIS for 24 communes in Kinshasa, for values including commune total area (km²), KDE-Count, KDE-Mean, KDE-standard deviation, KDE-Min and KDE-Max (Kafi et al., 2021). Km²

- Next, zonal statistics were calculated for 24 communes. The computed values included commune total area (km²), KDE-Count, KDE Mean, KDE standard deviation, KDE-Min and KDE-Max.

$$KDE_{mean} = \frac{1}{A} \int_A KDE(x) dx \quad (3)$$

where Mean KDE value extracted per commune polygon A .

- Using the data generated from zonal statistics, Pearson correlation was analyzed in Origin Pro, using a two-tailed test of significance (Liu et al., 2017).

$$r = \frac{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})^2 \sum(y_i - \bar{y})^2}} \quad (4)$$

2-tailed test, $\alpha = 0.05$, linear fit: $y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x$.

- Next, regression analysis (Kanishka et al., 2022) was carried out to predict the mean Kernel Density Estimate (KDE - Mean) based on predictors including population density, population raw counts, and waste collection service (binary: existing = 1, absent = 0). The model included an intercept (β_0), coefficients (β_1, β_2) for each predictor, and an error term (ϵ), with R^2 indicating explained variance.

$$KDE_{mean} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Pop}_{density} + \beta_2 \text{Area}_{km2} + \beta_3 \text{Dumpsites} + \epsilon \quad (5)$$

R^2 =explained variance, n = communes.

- Using zonal statistics data and demographic metrics, composite health risk index was then calculated to rank the communes based the level of vulnerability through exposure to waste dumpsites.

$$\text{Risk} = \text{Pop}_{density} \times \text{Dumpsites} \times KDE_{mean} \div \text{Area}_{km2} \quad (6)$$

Critical threshold >2.0 .

- Buffer analysis is extensively used in studies assessing hazards of various nature as well as environmental and ecological risks (Wang et al., 2024; Ya et al., 2019). Implemented using geographic information tools, buffer zones are created around points representing the features of interest, to represent scale influence zones. In this study, circular buffers of radius = 300 m were created around dumpsites as a first step in proximity analysis involving water bodies and human settlements. These buffers were designed to help unfold the patterns of potential waste pollutants' dispersion range in the study area.

$$B = (p, r) = \{q \mid |q - p| \leq r\} \quad (7)$$

where p = dumpsite point, r = buffer class, q = points within buffer zones

Findings

From the geospatial and statistical analysis in QGIS 3.44, Origin Pro 2025b and MS-Excel, the following results were obtained:

Kernel Density Estimation

Nearest-neighbor analysis computed on dumpsites points revealed a highly clustered distribution of ($n=213$ sites) with $Observed_{MD} = 628$ m; expected mean distance = 5,547 m; NN index = 0.11; and $Z = -24.76$). Therefore, the kernel bandwidth was fixed at 1 km. Figure 2 below shows the heatmap of waste dumpsites' distribution in Kinshasa city.

Detailed distribution patterns including counts of sites, hot and cold spots' distribution are shown in Table 1 on zonal statistics. Computation of zonal statistics generated data for 23 communes out of the 24 in Kinshasa. Maluku commune was excluded for missing data. The KDE standard deviation ranged from 0.1 to 2.2 across Kinshasa communes which highlights varying clustering intensity—low SD (0.1) in sparse areas like Nsele indicates uniform low density, while high SD (2.2) in hotspots in Makala and Bumbu shows concentrated variability.

Correlation Analysis

To examine statistical linkages between dumpsite density (KDE Mean) and demographic drivers, Pearson correlations were computed across 23 Kinshasa Communes ($\alpha=0.05$), see Table 2 in Appendix.

In the absence of recent census data, the demographic information used in this study was obtained from modeling figures published by Luwesi and Kazaku (2024) in their assessment of urbanization patterns and their effects on urban ecosystems in Kinshasa.

Figure 2. Heatmap of Dumpsites' Distribution in Kinshasa

Source: the authors

Note: *Bold colors indicate higher dumpsite density hotspots (≥ 9 sites/km²). Decreasing boldness and lighter shades show respectively smaller concentration of dumpsites per area, and the cold spots.

Table 1. Zonal Statistics

Commune	Area_km ²	KDEcount	KDEmean	KDEstdev	KDEmin	KDEmax
Lingwala	2880	83971	2.18202246	0.921464942	0.233438477	4.612006187
Kinshasa	2870	93189	2.642456539	1.344288751	0.473556608	5.425111771
Barumbu	4720	137786	2.060252313	0.96816222	0.09881831	4.821402073
Gombe	29330	304390	1.047641253	1.008978902	2.3172E-11	4.246908188
Ngiri Ngiri	3400	92665	2.139107269	0.840816937	0.477623105	4.300651073
Ngaba	4000	83429	0.801998576	0.538714976	1.19E-13	1.784580827
Kasa Vubu	5040	117579	2.25411449	0.925725712	0.391917855	5.467849255
Kintambo	2720	121461	1.475065855	0.965188519	3.11567E-07	3.798649311
Matete	4880	131082	0.941931837	1.030937233	1.5474E-11	4.075418949
Masina	69730	243003	0.644940577	0.714061756	6.77E-13	2.999953747
Ndjili	11400	218946	0.611840577	0.487949214	5.2413E-11	3.522473574
Makala	5600	139259	1.86771726	2.255299698	7.60217E-10	9.275389671
Bumbu	5300	121454	2.488429353	2.121409756	4.05E-11	9.240321159
Kalamu	6640	183702	2.640583818	1.296454376	0.20363529	5.683762074
Lemba	23700	415122	1.04102585	0.808269687	1.5743E-11	3.828360081
Limete	67600	433929	0.970245882	0.89943747	1.73852E-10	4.072762966
Ngaliema	244300	1119668	0.711906769	0.776543127	5.111E-12	4.890305519
Kinsenso	16600	186727	0.960796576	1.216430014	2.6907E-11	4.724458218
Mont-Ngafula	358920	325791	0.527747012	0.642569343	4.272E-12	3.774374485
Kimbanseke	237780	383051	0.578741104	0.497844491	4.5493E-11	1.999981880
Selembao	23160	320984	0.866275493	0.914735692	7.226E-12	5.752876759
Nsele	898.8	21645	0.150796836	0.153872431	2.46136E-09	0.708075643
Bandalungwa	6820	213941	1.570879044	1.274512857	3.6082E-11	4.961695671

Note: *Zonal statistics of continuous KDE across Kinshasa communes. Selected examples: Mean KDE—Kinshasa/Kalamu=2.6, Nsele=0.1; Max KDE—Makala/Bumbu=9.2, Nsele=0.7 (raster: min=7.8, max=9.2, mean=1.0, SD=1.1), n = 23.

Source: the authors

Figures 3 and 4 show linear regression explaining the relationships between population raw counts, population density and KDE-Mean values in Kinshasa.

Figure 3. Linear fit KDE mean _ Population density

Note: *KDE Mean exhibits negligible correlation with Population density: $y = 1.37 - 8.67 \times 10^{-5}x$ ($r = -0.0218$, $p = 0.9 > 0.05$), statistically insignificant.

Source: the authors

Figure 4. Linear fit: KDE Mean - Population

Note: *Very low correlation between KDE means and Population $y = 1.90 - 6.06 \times 10^{-7}x$ ($r = -0.376$, $p = 0.078 > 0.05$). Marginally significant.

Source: the authors

Tables 3 and 4 depict regression models predicting dumpsite KDE-Mean against population metrics and waste collection service (binary: existing = 1, absent = 0) across Kinshasa communes. Both models show low explanatory power ($R^2 = 0.20, 0.12$), indicating that population density and collection service predict neither raw counts nor spatial clustering of dumpsites. However, raw dumpsite counts outperformed KDE with ($R^2 = 0.20$ vs 0.12), revealing stronger baseline waste persistence (intercept 10.77 vs 1.59 , $p < 0.001$ vs $p = 0.09$) and marginal density effects ($\beta = -0.010$, $p = 0.065$).

Table 3. Dumpsites Count Regression

Parameter	β	p-value
Intercept	10.77	<0.001 **
Population density	-0.01	0.065 -
Collection service	-2.7	0.207

Note: * $R^2 = 0.2$ (20% variance explained). N= 23 communes

Source: the authors

Table 4. Kernel Density Estimation Regression

Parameter	β	p-value
Intercept	1.59	0.09
Population	-2.3	>0.50
Collection service	-0.53	>0.90

Note: * $R^2 = 0.12$ (12% variance explained). N= 23 communes.

Source: the authors

Health Risk Integration

To quantify population exposure to dumpsite hazards, a composite health risk index was computed as (Population density × Dumpsites count × KDE Mean) / Commune area across 23 Kinshasa communes. Critical risks were found for Kinshasa and Kintambo communes, with composite risk values > 2 (see Table 5).

Table 5. Health Risk Assessment from Dumpsites in 23 Communes in Kinshasa

Commune	Population density/ km ²	Area_km ²	Dumpsites	KDE Mean	Composite risk
Lingwala	73.36	2880	8	2.18	0.44
Kinshasa	316.59	2870	7	2.64	2.04
Barumbu	137.08	4720	8	2.06	0.48
Gombe	8.1	29330	11	1.05	0.00
Ngiri Ngiri	136.02	3400	5	2.14	0.43
Ngaba	117.2	4000	1	0.80	0.02
Kasa Vubu	76.4	5040	8	2.25	0.27
Kintambo	500.47	2720	8	1.48	2.17
Matete	160.11	4880	5	0.94	0.15
Masina	21.64	69730	4	0.64	0.00
Ndjili	96.48	11400	4	0.61	0.02
Makala	134.46	5600	9	1.87	0.40
Bumbu	174.94	5300	9	2.49	0.74
Kalamu	129.18	6640	19	2.64	0.98
Lemba	39.65	23700	14	1.04	0.02
Limete	14.15	67600	10	0.97	0.00
Ngaliema	9.36	244300	23	0.71	0.00
Kinsenso	58.1	16600	6	0.96	0.02
Mont-Ngafula	2.17	358920	5	0.53	0.00
Kimbanseke	7.35	237780	7	0.58	0.00
Selembao	35.35	23160	9	0.87	0.01
Nsele	858.953	898.8	0	0.15	0.00
Bandalungwa	107.71	6820	10	1.57	0.25

Note: *Composite risk was calculated based on = (Dumpsites × Population density × KDE Mean) / Area. Two communes exceed a threshold >2.

Source: the authors

Proximity to Major Water Bodies and Buildings

Proximity analysis for water bodies and human settlements was carried out within buffer radius= 300 m. Buffers were created within the coordinate reference system, “CRS”: EPSG:4050 – RGRDC 2005 / Congo TM zone 16(the DR Congo’s national coordinate reference system for Kinshasa). The next step involved intersecting the buffers with water bodies’ polygons to compute the number and area falling within the influence zone (see Figure 5).

We calculated the number of intersecting points of each water ecosystem class within the buffer zones as an indicator of spatial exposure. Based on the total number of connection points across the buffer, exposure risk was categorized into “high”, “medium”, “low”(see Table 6).

Figure 5. Dumpsite Proximity to Major Water Bodies (300m Buffer) – Kinshasa/Bukavu
Source: the authors

Note: *Based on the Geofabrik’s OSM(open street map) data, water points were automatically classified into water bodies, riverbanks, wetland and reservoirs. Intersection calculation using 300 m buffers around dumpsites generated fifty-one intersection points(n=53), with most dumpsites showing multiple intersecting points to these water points.

Table 6. Water Proximity Risk

Dumpsites	Latitude	Longitude	Reservoir	Riverbank	Water	Wetland	Total	Risk Index
Site 1	-4.375191	15.344643			3		3	Medium
Site 2	-4.409558	15.318634			3		3	Medium
Site 3	-4.387634	15.366129		2		3	5	High
Site 4	-4.344055	15.324512			3		3	Medium
Site 5	-4.346473	15.324929			4		4	Medium
Site 6	-4.353961	15.324651			1		1	Low
Site 7	-4.327933	15.296498			1		1	Low
Site 8	-4.311771	15.307753			4		4	Medium
Site 9	-4.442088	15.393598	6		1		7	High
Site 10	-4.381585	15.361182		1	1		2	Low
Site 11	-4.386452	15.361182			1	1	2	Low
Site 12	-4.298384	15.310655			1		1	Low
Site 13	-4.377039	15.346677			1		1	Low
Site 14	-4.329911	15.244677			1		1	Low
Site 15	-4.3088	15.306066			3		3	Medium
Site 16	-4.365461	15.389944				1	1	Low
Site 17	-4.301442	15.30546			1		1	Low
Site 18	-4.410421	15.404286		1			1	Low
Site 19	-4.410488	15.42987				1	1	Low
Site 20	-4.341174	15.329677			8		8	High
Grand total			6	4	37	6	53	

Note: *In total, 53 connection points were established with water points(N=53) from 20 dumpsites. Three sites show high exposure risk for the water points in the vicinity (300 m) of waste dumpsites, based on the formula:=IF(Total2≥5,"High",IF(Total2≥3,"Medium",IF(Total2≥1,"Low","None"))).

Source: the authors

This result reveals evident to severe exposure of water resources to contaminants from waste materials in the dumpsites. For better risk assessment, a heatmap of these 53 intersection points was next computed, then overlaid on water bodies' polygons across communes' boundaries to highlight the areas and dumpsites necessitating urgent intervention to mitigate contamination risks in neighboring water ecosystem (See Figure 6).

Figure 6. Dumpsites within 300 m from Water Resources _ Heatmap

Source: the authors

Note: *Vertically ascending from lighter areas through medium bold to darker shades, the density of dumpsites with 300m of water bodies is shown, darker zones representing major hotspots of contamination risk for waterbodies.

To analyze the spatial exposure of human settlements, a first step involved computing centroids for buildings in the “CRS”: EPSG:4050 – RGRDC 2005 / Congo TM zone 16. This approach allowed to reduce the visual clutter and computational load from the detailed building dataset. The created centroids’ layer was then overlaid with dumpsites buffers(radius = 300 m) for proximity analysis(see Figure 7).

Figure 7. Building Counts within 300m of Dumpsites.

Source: the authors

Note: *Among 172 dumpsites, 11 sites expose over 12000 buildings comprising buildings within 300m-representing 22% of total exposure-indicating highly concentrated public health risks, 41 sites count 26674 buildings within 300m-47%, representing high risks. In total, 56765 buildings were found within 300 m of waste dumpsites accross the total study area.

In addition, we counted the number of building centroids falling inside the buffer polygon. Counts were summarized to obtain the number of buildings located within 300 m of a dumpsite. Based on these counts, exposure was categorized into, “critical”, “high”, “medium”, “medium-low”, and “low”(as detailed in Table 7 and Figure 8).

Table 7. Dumpsite Exposure by Risk Class (n=172 sites)

Risk index	Dumpsites	Building	(%)
Critical	11	12475	22%
High	41	26674	47%
Medium	62	15044	27%
Medium-low	21	1563	3%
Low	37	1009	2%
Grand Total	172	56765	100%

Source: the authors

Note: *Risk strata were created using the following count thresholds:

=IF(Buildings≥1000,"Critical",IF(Buildings≥500,"High",IF(Buildings≥100,"Medium",IF(Buildings≥50,"Medium-low", IF(Buildings≥2,"Low"))))

Figure 8. Distribution of Building Exposure among the 172 Dumpsites

Source: the authors

Note: *Boxplots grouped by risk class depict the distribution of exposed buildings (n=56,765). High-risk sites dominate the total exposure (n=26674 buildings), and fewer buildings(1009) fall in the low-risk class. Critical sites appear as outliers with more than 1000 exposed buildings each, indicating a small number of locations with extremely concentrated exposure.

Discussion

Findings from the current study show uneven distribution of waste dumpsites across Kinshasa city, with high concentration of sites in Makala and Bumbu. These two communes exhibit dumpsites' density hotspots ≥ 2.1 sites/km². Other sites of dense distribution are seen in communes of Kinshasa, Kalamu, Kisenso, Ngaliema, Bandalungwa, Lingwala, Selembao, Barumbu and Gombe. Previous studies extensively state the rapid pace with which dumpsites have been proliferating in

recent decades for various hypothesized explanatory factors that combine rapid urban growth and high population density, informal economy and poverty, weak urban governance and institutional fragmentation (Sendezzo et al., 2024; Simatele & Etambakonga, 2015). While some scholars support claims of environmental injustice in the hypothesized distribution of waste dumpsites in Kinshasa, the heatmap generated in this study ranks some rather wealthy communes _such as Gombe and Ngaliema_ close to the major dumpsites' hotspots. Investigating the implications of environmental justice in waste management in Kinshasa, Kubanza *et al.*, (2017) report an atypical waste collection service provided by the informal sector which consists of removing garbage from wealthier neighborhoods to afterward carry and dump it in the poor communities' settlements. While these claims might hold strong to some extent, the current study shows a rather common vulnerability of Kinshasa's overall urban ecosystems and populations to significant waste toxicity risks from dumpsites. This vulnerability amplifies among poorer communities with documented low accessibility to waste collection services that most fail to afford, preferring to dump in any public place in reach (Vuni et al., 2022). In addition to their hypothesized high contribution to waste dumping metrics, low-income households are additionally exposed to waste toxicity risks through unsupervised solid waste scavenging sector for survival (Simatele & Etambakonga, 2015). This study found no meaningful relationship between dumpsites clustering and population metrics _raw counts and density_ ($r = -0.376, -0.022$). These divergent patterns indicate compounded population-exposure risks beyond visual hotspots, as well as multi-dimensional drivers of dumpsites proliferation.

The health risks inherent to these uncontrolled dumpsites that emerge and grow in proximity to residential areas are increasingly pointed out in previous studies (Kang et al., 2023; Mangenda et al., 2022). These piles of waste avail breeding grounds for disease vectors such as mosquitoes, further amplifying malaria cases and spreading other diseases among the neighboring communities. Calculation of health composite risk in Kinshasa positioned Kinshasa and Kintambo communes above a threshold >2.0 , indicating their residents' increased vulnerability. This result, rather diverged from the proliferation patterns exhibited in the heatmap which located higher dumpsite density hotspots primarily in Makala and Bumbu. Further risk analysis comprised proximity of dumpsites to water bodies and human settlements. In QGIS 3.44, 300-meter buffers were created around the total number of dumpsites ($n=213$). Intersection calculation generated a total of 20 dumpsites, with a share of fifty-three intersection points ($n=53$) to water systems, with most dumpsites showing multiple intersections to one or more water class (from the OSM dataset, water classes included waterbody, riverbank, wetland and reservoir). This result evidence severe exposure of water resources to contaminants from waste materials in the dumpsites. The major rivers at risk include the Congo River in Pool Malebo, along with N'djili river. These results align with previous studies that established significant contamination in surface and groundwater in Kinshasa (Mufungizi et al., 2024; REGIDESO, 2019).

An expected connection failed to be established between dumpsites and Tshuenge river for which a recent pollution evaluation has been hypothesized as linked with waste dumping in river and its vicinity (Sifa et al., 2024). However, it could be posited that extending the buffer zone would drastically modify these findings, multiplying the intersection points between dumpsites and water bodies. Although, notwithstanding direct connectivity, open and unengineered waste dumpsites potently contaminate urban ecosystems including surface water through multiple vectors such as urban runoff and poorly managed wastewater (Sikder et al., 2024). Concerning proximity analysis for buildings, a total of 56765 buildings were counted within 300-meter of waste dumpsites. These buildings include houses, schools, hospitals, banks, churches, offices and all settlements involved in urbanites' daily activities. Among these 56765, distributed across a total of 172 dumpsites, 11 sites expose over 12000 buildings-representing 22% of total exposure-indicating highly concentrated public health risks. Moreover, 47% of the total number of sites (41) count 26674

buildings within 300m-, representing high risks. These results further emphasize health risks arising from direct contamination from dumpsites with high proximity to human settlements across Kinshasa city(Kang et al., 2024; Kubanza, 2017; Mangenda et al., 2022). As seen in critical zones, in most communes, such as Bumbu, Kalamu, and Kinshasa, dumpsites and buildings fusion with ambiguous delineations. These findings support Kang *et al.* (2024)'s conclusions positing high dumpsites' proximity as a major driver of elevated prevalence of typhoid fever and malaria in Bandalungwa and Bumbu municipalities.

Conclusions

The current study assessed the geospatial patterns of municipal solid waste dumpsites distribution across Kinshasa and their associated health and environmental risks. The findings revealed several dumpsites hotspots with observed variations in exposure risks. The communes of Makala and Bumbu showed elevated counts of dumpsites, while Kinshasa and Kintambo demonstrated critical health risk vulnerability (<2). However, water contamination exposure localized severe vulnerability in communes such as Kalamu, Limete, Kimbanseke, N'djili and Gombe. Bumbu and Makala are additionally found to have high concentration buildings within 300m buffers around dumpsites. These findings classify exposure offering multiple options for risk prioritization, essential for the DR Congo's context of resource constraints. Reproducing such approach across similar developing countries would be profitable to support low-cost decision-making to address waste management challenges. Demographic metrics were ruled out of being considered as major triggers of dumpsites' proliferation across municipalities. This result suggests the involvement of complex and multifaceted drivers in the current trends in dumpsites' spatial distribution, stemming likely from governance inadequacies. This study focused on a cross-sectional spatial analysis, overlooking temporal dynamics or chemical sampling for precise health and environmental risk assessment.

Key recommended directions for future investigations include:

- Longitudinal dumpsite monitoring using very high-resolution remote sensing imagery and advanced deep learning approaches,
- Finer-scale risk assessment (ward-level, n>1000)
- Geophysical and geochemical studies of the contaminant impact waste dumpsites in Kinshasa and other cities of the DR Congo.
- Large-scale soil, surface and groundwater, and crops' sampling for heavy metals/pathogens detection.
- Policy intervention trials

Data Availability

Data will be made available on reasonable request.

References

Adedinni, M. O., Arogundade, A. B., Ore, O. T., Adenika, C. I., Adebayo, A. S., Akinlade, G. O., ... & Oyekunle, J. A. O. (2023). Geophysical and geochemical study of the contaminant impact of

- Oke-Tage solid waste dumpsite, Southwestern Nigeria. . *Scientific Reports*, 13(1), 4704. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-31948-3>
- Bangani, L., Kabiti, H. M., Amoo, O., Nakin, M. D., Magayiyana, Z., & , & Ndhleve, S. (2025). Hotspots of illegal dumping of solid waste along the Mthatha River. *International Journal of Environment and Waste Management*, 37(3), 261-277. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJEW.M.2025.146867>
- Barles, S. (2014). History of waste management and the social and cultural representations of waste. In *The basic environmental history* (pp. 199-226). Springer International Publishing.
- Bédécarrats, F., Lafuente-Sampietro, Oriane, Leménager, Martin, Dominique Lukono Sowa. (2019). Building commons to cope with chaotic urbanization? Performance and sustainability of decentralized water services in the outskirts of Kinshasa. *Journal of Hydrology*, 573, 1096-1108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2016.07.023>
- Bundhoo, Z. M. (2018). Solid waste management in least developed countries: current status and challenges faced. *Journal of Material Cycles and Waste Management*, 20(3), 1867-1877. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10163-018-0728-3>
- Chen, Y. C. (2017). A tutorial on kernel density estimation and recent advances. . *Biostatistics & Epidemiology*, 1(1), 161–187. <https://doi.org/10.1080/24709360.2017.1396742>
- Chuma, G. B., Mondo, J. M., Ndeko, A. B., Akuzibwe, E. M., Bagula, E. M., & , & Mushagalusa, G. N. (2024). Quantification and valorization of compost derived from urban households' waste in Bukavu City, Eastern DR Congo. *Discover Sustainability*, 5(1), 102. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43621-024-00283-6>
- Diambu, A. N. e., & Mehmet, Ç. (2024). Sustainable Reuse of Food Waste in the Democratic Republic of the Congo for Biocomposite Reinforcement. *Sürdürülebilir Çevre Dergisi*, 4, 41-54. <https://doi.org/10.62816/cevder.1497294>
- Eckert-Gallup, A., & Martin, N. (2016). Kernel density estimation (KDE) with adaptive bandwidth selection for environmental contours of extreme sea states.
- Ekeu-Wei, I. T., Azuma, K. I., & , & Ogunmuyiwa, F. B. B. (2018). Assessment of environmental impact of solid waste dumpsites using remote sensing. *Nigerian journal of technology*, 37(1), 275-285. <https://doi.org/10.4314/njt.v37i1.36>
- Fazzo, L., Manno, V., Lavarone, I., Minelli, G., De Santis, M., Beccaloni, E., ... & , & Comba, P. (2023). The health impact of hazardous waste landfills and illegal dumps contaminated sites: An epidemiological study at ecological level in Italian Region. *Frontiers in public health*, 11, 996960. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2023.996960>
- Gonzenbach, B., & , & Coad, A. (2007). *Solid waste management and the Millennium Development Goals*. Collaborative Working Group on Solid Waste Management in Low-and Middle-income Countries.
- INS. (2024). *Enquête Démographique et de Santé III (EDS-RDC III) 2023 - 2024*. Institut National des Statistiques Retrieved from <https://www.unicef.org/drcongo/media/12816/file/RDC-EDS-III-resume.pdf>
- Kafi, K. M., Barau, A. S., & Aliyu, A. (2021). The effects of windstorm in African medium-sized cities: An analysis of the degree of damage using KDE hotspots and EF-scale matrix. *International journal of disaster risk reduction*, 55, 102070. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2021.102070>
- Kang, Y., O., Yabar, H., Lubula, K., Mizunoya, T., & Higano, Y. (2023). Environmental and economic performances of municipal solid waste management strategies based on LCA method: A case study of Kinshasa. *Heliyon*(Elsevier). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e14372>

- Kang, Y. O., Yabar, H., Karume L., K., Mizunoya, T., & Higano, Y. (2024). Geospatial Analysis of Malaria and Typhoid Prevalence Due to Waste Dumpsite Exposure in Kinshasa Districts with and Without Waste Services: A Case Study of Bandalungwa and Bumbu, Democratic Republic of Congo. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 21. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph21111495>
- Kanishka, T., Chinmay, R., & Harshvardhan, M. M. (2022). Chapter 4 - Regression analysis. In S. K. K. Rajiv Pandey, Neeraj kumar Singh, Parul Verma, (Ed.), *Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning for EDGE Computing*, (pp. 53-63). Academic Press. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-824054-0.00007-1>.
- Katembo, A. K., Nkongolo, J. J. M., et , & Nsele, C. M. (2025). Impact of sorting and recycling of household waste on the urban development of Limete in Kinshasa. . In U. d. Kinshasa (Ed.), *Repères et Perspectives Economiques* (Vol. 9(1), pp. 106-128).
- Kubanza, N. S., Das, Dillip Kumar, et Simatele, Danny. (2017). Some happy, others sad: exploring environmental justice in solid waste management in Kinshasa, The Democratic Republic of Congo. . *Local Environment*, 22(5), 595-620. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2016.1242120>
- Kubanza, N. S. a., & Simatele, D. (2015). Social and environmental injustices in solid waste management in sub-Saharan Africa: a study of Kinshasa, the Democratic Republic of Congo. *Local environment: The International Journal of Justice and Sustainability*, 21:7, 866-882. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2015.1038985>
- Lenzo, R. S., Kut, J.-P. K., Kashemukunda, K. N., Nsiama, K. K., Lelo, G. K., Kra A., Wa Luvuvamu, A. N., & K.L., L. (2024). Contribution To The Study Of Assessing Rainfall Patterns As Indicators Of Climate Change: A Study In Kinshasa City, Democratic Republic Of Congo. . *Geological Behavior (GBR)*, 8(2), 136-145. <https://doi.org/10.26480/gbr.02.2024.136.145>
- Liu, A.-N., Wang, L.-L., Li, H.-P., Gong, J., & Liu, X.-H. (2017). Correlation between posttraumatic growth and posttraumatic stress disorder symptoms based on Pearson correlation coefficient: A meta-analysis. *The Journal of nervous and mental disease*, 205(5), 380-389. <https://doi.org/10.1097/NMD.0000000000000605>
- LUKAFULU. (2025). *Cartographie participative des déchets à Kinshasa* (<https://lukafulu.com/reports/view/243>)
- Luwesi N., C., & , & Kazaku, K. (2024). Autopromotion de l'habitat, cause principale de la destruction de l'environnement dans la ville de Kinshasa, RDC (1974-2024). *Health-Environment Sustainability Journal*, 13(1), 1-27. https://www.academia.edu/119917445/Kazaku_Article_HES_J_202403224_prof_FINAL
- Mangenda, H. H., Mulaba, P., et , & Kiawutua, A. (2020). Gestion des déchets ménagers dans la ville de Kinshasa: Enquête sur la perception des habitants et propositions. . *Environnement, Ingénierie & Développement*, N 83, 19-26. <https://doi.org/10.4267/dechets-sciences-techniques.4272>
- Mangenda, H. H., Simbu A., V., Nsungu D.N., Masamuna P., Muya Ml L., Lunda, M., & B., L. L. (2022). Analyse du système de gestion des décharges pirates et l'impact sanitaire et environnementale dans la commune de Kasavubu, ville de Kinshasa en République Démocratique du Congo. 1-18. <https://hal.science/hal-03722732v1>
- Maturano, J. G., Santana, J. D. M., Aguilar, S. L., & , & Hernández, M. S. (2024). Remote sensing of illegal dumps through supervised classification of satellite images: Application in Oaxaca, Mexico. *Geographical Research Letters*, 50(2), 157-177. <https://doi.org/10.18172/cig.6273>

- Mavakala, B. K., Sivalingam, P., Laffite, A., Mulaji, C. K., Giuliani, G., Mpiana, P. T., & J., P. (2022). Evaluation of heavy metal content and potential ecological risks in soil samples from wild solid waste dumpsites in developing country under tropical conditions. *Environmental Challenges*, 7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envc.2022.100461>
- Mufungizi, I., Loola, R., Kabulo, J., Diakondua, R., Kawayu, H., Bongeli, R., Musitu, J., Kasongo, K., & Akilimali, A. (2024). Assessment of interactions between raw water from the N'Djili river, groundwater and water treated by the Water Distribution Administration in Kinshasa, Democratic Republic of Congo. *International Journal of Innovation and Applied Studies*, 41(4), 946-956. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10501141>
- Nagpure, A. S. (2019). Assessment of quantity and composition of illegal dumped municipal solid waste (MSW) in Delhi. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 141, 54-60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2018.10.012>
- Navasardova, E. S., Makarova, T. I., Zaharin, A. N., Kolesnikova, K. V., & , & Nutrikhin, R. V. (2020). Regulating waste management: national experience and international practice. *J. Environ. Treat. Tech.* , 8(4), 1574-1580. <https://doi.org/10.47277/JETT/1580>
- Ngweme, G. N., Emmanuel K.A., Dhafer, M. M. A. S., Paola M. M., Guillaume M. K., Crispin K. M., Jean-Paul O., & Poté, J. W. (2020). Heavy metal concentration in irrigation water, soil and dietary risk assessment of *Amaranthus viridis* grown in peri-urban areas in Kinshasa, Democratic Republic of the Congo. . *Watershed Ecology and the Environment*, 2, 16-24. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wsee.2020.07.001>
- Ndala, D. D. (2024). De Matete à Kinshasa [Master's thesis, Université d'Ottawa]. uO Research. <https://ruor.uottawa.ca/server/api/core/bitstreams/154dc25a-313b-4dfe-9b17-3e51f42a9577/content>
- Nsindu, G. N., Tshisuaka, B. K., & K., K. A. (2023). Impact des déchets ménagers sur l'environnement et la santé dans la périphérie de Kinshasa, RDC. *African Scientific Journal (ASJ)*, 3(16), 147-172. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7648565>
- Nwankwoala, H. O., & , & Offor, S. C. (2018). Contamination Assessment of Soil and Groundwater within and around Semi-controlled Solid Waste Dumpsites in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. . *Journal of Waste Recycling*, 3(2:8), 1-10.
- Omokaro, G. O., Michael, I., & , & Evgenievich, P. V. (2024). Assessing the environmental and health implications of waste disposal: a case study of Africa's largest dumping site. *Journal of Geography, Environment and Earth Science International*, 28(5), 16-30. <https://doi.org/10.9734/jgeesi/2024/v28i5767>
- Constitution de la République Démocratique du Congo du 18 février 2006, (2006).
- Law n° 08/012 of July 31st, 2008, on the free administration of the provinces, (2008a). <https://leganet.cd/Legislation/Droit%20Public/Administration.ter/LOI.31.07.2008.provinces.htm>
- Parliament. (2008b). Loi organique n° 08/016 du 07 octobre 2008 portant composition, organisation et fonctionnement des Entités Territoriales Décentralisées et leurs rapports avec l'Etat et les Provinces. <https://www.leganet.cd/Legislation/Droit%20Public/Administration.ter/L.08.16.17.10.2008.htm>
- Law No. 11/009 of 9 July 2011 relating to fundamental principles relating to environmental protection (2011).

- REGIDESO. (2019). *Etude d'impact environnemental et social (EIES) du projet de construction d'une station de captage d'eau brute sur le fleuve Congo et d'une usine de traitement d'eau potable sur le site de la REGIDESO/Binzà - Ozone à Kinshasa*. W. B. Group. <https://documents.worldbank.org/en/publication/documents-reports/documentdetail/572071502790554470>
- Remigios, M. V. (2010). An overview of the management practices at solid waste disposal sites in African cities and towns. *Journal of sustainable development in Africa*, 12(7), 233-239.
- Rodriguez, Y. P., Holy, H. M., Alexis, V. S., Ruffin, B. N., Rosine, M. a., & Jules, A. K. (2022). Monitoring of air quality in Kinshasa by mobile analyses of atmospheric NO₂ in different geographical locations. *Environnement, Ingénierie & Développement (EID)*, 86, 13-21. <https://doi.org/10.46298/eid.2022.8379>
- Scheinberg, A., Wilson, D. C., & Rodic, L. (2010). *Solid Waste Management in the World's Cities: Water and Sanitation in the World's Cities 2010*. E. o. b. o. UN-HABITAT.
- Sendezo, J. G., Okintambolo, O. L., Mutela, A. L., Lokombe, C. S., Ambur, J.-A. O., Lenge, J. M. L., Wataie, K. K., Lokangu, L. T., Mbuyi, D. M., Kabongo, A. B., Wa Mufuta, J. M., Musitu, B. J., Tangali, C. N. a., & M., M. A. (2024). Analyse environnementale et sociale de l'état de lieu des inondations à kinshasa. Cas des quartiers Yolo-Nord et Kimbangu I dans la commune de Kalamu. *Revue Internationale de la Recherche Scientifique (Revue-IRS)*, 2(5), 2598-2614. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13899889>
- Sifa, D.-B. K. M., Nzadi, P. L., et , & Mayala, B. N.-K. (2024). Impact des activités anthropiques sur la qualité physico-chimique des eaux de la rivière Tshuenge localisée à l'Est de Kinshasa/RD Congo. *International Journal of Biological and Chemical Sciences*, 18(3), 1115-1127. <https://doi.org/10.4314/ijbcs.v18i3.31>
- Sikder, S., Toha, M., & Mostafizur R., M. (2024). An overview on municipal solid waste characteristics and its impacts on environment and human health. . In *Landfill Impacts, Characterization and Valorisation* (pp. 135-155.). Technical Landfills and Waste Management.
- Simatele, D. e., & Etambakonga, C. L. (2015). Scavenging for solid waste in Kinshasa: A livelihood strategy for the urban poor in the Democratic Republic of Congo. . *Habitat International*, 49, 266-274. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.habitatint.2015.05.029>
- Uhri, L., & , & Nemes, O. (2024). Examination of environmental legislation (related administrative law and some criminal and civil law) and sanctions for illegal waste dumping in the V4+ countries (Czech Republic, Poland, Hungary, Slovakia and Slovenia). *J. Agric. Env't L*, 19, 225. <https://doi.org/10.21029/JAEL.2024.36.225>
- UNEP. (2024). *Global Waste Management Outlook 2024 - Beyond an age of waste - Turning rubbish into a resource*.
- Vuni, A., Mangenda, H. H., Pucla, F., Wamba, E., Mutayiya, F., Masamuna, P., Nzuzi, F., Komanda, J., & Mbudi, C. (2022). Study of current urban waste management in Kinshasa by observation along university avenue. *Environnement, Ingénierie & Développement* 3-11. <https://doi.org/10.46298/eid.2022.9250>
- Vuppaladadiyam, S. S. V., Vuppaladadiyam, A. K., Sahoo, A., Urgunde, A., Murugavelh, S., Šrámek, V., Pohořelý, M., Trakal, L., Bhattacharya, S., Sarmah, A. K., Shah, K., & Pant.K.K. (2024). Waste to energy: Trending key challenges and current technologies in waste plastic management. *Science of the Total Environment*, 913. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.169436>.

Wang, Z., Chen, J., Lian, Z., Li, F., Pang, L., & Xin, Y. (2024). Influence of buffer distance on environmental geological hazard susceptibility assessment. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 31(6), 9582-9595. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-023-31739-3>

Wilson, D. C., Rodic, L., Cowing, M. J., Velis, C. A., Whiteman, A. D., Scheinberg, A., ... & , & Oelz, B. (2015). Wasteaware'benchmark indicators for integrated sustainable waste management in cities. *Waste Management*, 35, 329-342. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2014.10.006>

Ya, X., Jingcai, L., Lu, D., Yuqiang, L., Weishi, L., Changxing, N., & , & Qifei, H. (2019). Buffering distance between hazardous waste landfill and water supply wells in a shallow aquifer. . *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 211, 1180-1189. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.11.161>.

Appendix

Table 2. Pearson Correlations(r)

		Area_km ²	Population	P-density	Collect	Count	Mean	Stdev	Min	Max
Area_km ²	<i>r</i>	1	0.51882	-0.34124	-0.05625	0.62743	-0.45098	-0.30482	-0.25552	-0.2109
Area_km ²	<i>p-value</i>	--	0.01119	0.11104	0.79877	0.00135	0.03079	0.15729	0.23929	0.33407
Population	<i>r</i>	0.51882	1	-0.05247	0.05578	0.69225	-0.37634	-0.14469	-0.35541	-0.11946
Pop_2024	<i>p-value</i>	0.01119	--	0.81206	0.80042	2.52E-04	0.07674	0.5101	0.09605	0.58718
Pop_density	<i>r</i>	-0.34124	-0.05247	1	-0.1102	-0.42792	-0.02183	-0.1464	0.05789	-0.25512
Pop_density	<i>p-value</i>	0.11104	0.81206	--	0.61669	0.04165	0.92124	0.50506	0.79305	0.24006
Collection	<i>r</i>	-0.05625	0.05578	-0.1102	1	-0.06708	-0.34135	-0.35932	-0.28697	-0.45833
Collection	<i>p-value</i>	0.79877	0.80042	0.61669	--	0.76106	0.11091	0.0922	0.1843	0.02784
KDEcount	<i>r</i>	0.62743	0.69225	-0.42792	-0.06708	1	-0.37096	-0.16624	-0.31049	-0.02098
KDEcount	<i>p-value</i>	0.00135	2.52E-04	0.04165	0.76106	--	0.0814	0.44838	0.14932	0.9243
KDEmean	<i>r</i>	-0.45098	-0.37634	-0.02183	-0.34135	-0.37096	1	0.65476	0.69207	0.65807
KDEmean	<i>p-value</i>	0.03079	0.07674	0.92124	0.11091	0.0814	--	6.98E-04	2.53E-04	6.42E-04
KDEstdev	<i>r</i>	-0.30482	-0.14469	-0.1464	-0.35932	-0.16624	0.65476	1	0.07769	0.93302
KDEstdev	<i>p-value</i>	0.15729	0.5101	0.50506	0.0922	0.44838	6.98E-04	--	0.72458	<0.0001
KDEmin	<i>r</i>	-0.25552	-0.35541	0.05789	-0.28697	-0.31049	0.69207	0.07769	1	0.1438
KDEmin	<i>p-value</i>	0.23929	0.09605	0.79305	0.1843	0.14932	2.53E-04	0.72458	--	0.51271
KDEmax	<i>r</i>	-0.2109	-0.11946	-0.25512	-0.45833	-0.02098	0.65807	0.93302	0.1438	1
KDEmax	<i>p-value</i>	0.33407	0.58718	0.24006	0.02784	0.9243	6.42E-04	<0.0001	0.51271	--

Note: *Two-tailed test of significance was used

Source: the authors

